

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF ACHIEVING SOCIAL CONSENSUS IN ENSURING PUBLIC SECURITY

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Abstract: this article analyzes the theoretical and methodological foundations of achieving social consensus in the provision of public safety.

Key words: security, public safety, consensus, social consensus, social contract, social compromise.

Due to the increasing number of threats and attacks on social stability in the world, the task of developing social mechanisms aimed at achieving social consensus in ensuring public safety is becoming more urgent. The dynamic analysis of public security shows that the need to implement social contract, agreement and social compromise policy is increasing in order to ensure the stability of societies. The need to ensure public safety created an opportunity for a new approach to social conflicts. Therefore, it is important to analyze the scope and forms of manifestation of conflicts. For this reason, there is a need for political research aimed at studying the problems of achieving social consensus in the provision of public security.

Important theoretical and fundamental studies are being conducted by the world's leading scientific research institutes and research centers dedicated to the issues of achieving social consensus in the provision of public safety. On the basis of these links, it is concluded that one of the important aspects of studying conflicts in the field of social relations in the provision of public safety is the issue of managing the development of dialectical conflicts in the development of society. Therefore, there is a need for a systematic study of the issues of achieving social consensus in the provision of public safety.

In the new development strategy of Uzbekistan, "improving preventive mechanisms aimed at preventing factors that cause social threats, improving the social and moral environment, preventing the influence of foreign ideas and eliminating their problems through systematic work with those who have fallen under their influence"[1] is a priority and main goal. designated as one of the directions. In this way, the improvement of the mechanisms of ensuring public safety, this is not unanimity and approval of everything with one voice, but getting rid of the characteristics of rigid thinking and one-sidedness, forming the unity of

the state and the people based on the diversity and diversity of opinions, strengthening the trust of the population in the state and society. is aimed at achieving. That's why the dialectical analysis of social consensus in ensuring public safety is gaining relevance based on new approaches.

In this article, we will analyze the social necessity of ensuring public safety, preventing threats against it, the manifestation of threats and their causes, and social consequences. For this, first of all, it would be appropriate to review the content, social content of the concepts of security and public safety.

Chambers' Dictionary defines "security" as "the state, means, or sense of security." This concept is explained in connection with the loss of "overcomprehensibility, anxiety", "confidence", "stability"[2].

In modern literature, the concept of "security" is considered as a system of conditions and factors that develop on the basis of the object's limitation of its functions and its internal laws [3]. Also, security is described as protection from conditions and factors that pose a threat to an individual or society [4].

It should be emphasized that many definitions given to the concept of "security" are criticized by scientists and practitioners. In our opinion, the main reason for the lack of clarity in many definitions is that the definition of the concept does not take into account risk, which is considered the dialectical opposite of security. It is the study of the causes of the occurrence of danger that allows us to give a more precise definition of the concept of "security". As stated by G.A. Atamanov, security, as its derivative, acquires meaning in connection with risk [5]. According to the author, "security" represents the state of the object in the presence of internal and external influences, which is related to the violation of the mechanism of vital existence of the system. It would not be appropriate for him to perceive any threat as a danger, security comes from overcoming danger.

Russian scientist V.I. According to Dahl, the term "security" is a complex concept whose meaning seems intuitively self-explanatory. The concept of "security" has a subjective meaning according to the usual perception of people, that is, security is the state of protection of the subject from negative factors that harm him. In other words, "security" can be defined as "absence of danger" [6].

Thus, the concept of "security" can be interpreted as the absence of danger to someone or something.

Today, there are different definitions of security, and their authors are based on different criteria. Sometimes it is imagined that "security is a condition, traditions of development and conditions of life activity..."[7]. In addition, if

security limits the progress of innovation, then it can lead to stagnation, conservatism, regression. The security system should not only prevent changes in quantity or quality, but also help to overcome the old forms without causing harm to the society and the individual. In many cases, it is believed that revealing the concept of "security" through the terms "protection", "protected", "protecting" narrows its meaning. To protect is interpreted as closing something, putting a barrier on something; it can be called a thing, an object, an event, a guard, an obstacle to someone, something, and finally, a shield in the correct and figurative sense when we say it simply. In modern encyclopedic dictionaries, this word is interpreted in this way or in this way. However, we did not find the interpretation of the important property and function of security - reducing, eliminating, and warning risks and threats, which were thoroughly disclosed in the literature. In particular, the meaning of the word "to protect" reflects an important function of security, but it does not imply a complete meaning.

Much of the literature defines "safety" as "the absence of potential harm." These definitions, which can be taken as a basis, reflect two principles of security.

The principle that follows from the first definition is security, which is based on the criterion of qualitative security. This criterion can take two values: 1 (security is ensured) or 0 (security is not ensured). If, during the assessment of the security situation, it is concluded that the interests important to the individual, society and the state are protected, then the criterion for ensuring security is considered equal to 1 and it is decided that security is ensured. However, if it is assumed that "full" security is provided, then the possibility of harm from an incident is eliminated. If, during the assessment of the security situation, it is concluded that the interests important to the individual, society and the state are not protected, then the security criterion is considered equal to 0 and it is decided that security is not ensured.

The safety principle from the second definition always relies on the presumption that the damage will occur, based on the assumption that "complete" safety cannot be guaranteed. Thus, in different cultures of the world, generally the same perceptions of security and threat have been formed, in which the emphasis is placed on the intuitions and concerns of the individual about his current and future situation.

That is, safety for a person is first of all knowing and feeling that he is protected from various types of dangerous actions.

As a result of the analysis, we present the following definition: ensuring personal safety or eliminating the threat is considered as a state of public consciousness, in which the existing quality levels of life of the whole society and an individual are accepted as reliable. Because it gives citizens real opportunities to meet their current natural and social needs and reasonable confidence in the future.

The following opinion is also expressed about the occurrence of risks: The occurrence of risks can be different according to certain conditions. In this regard, some authors, despite the fact that its implementation is a logically complex issue, use the concept of threat as a concept that specifies a certain risk and reflects the probability of its occurrence [8].

As for the analysis of the concept of "public safety", it should be noted that many views on the definition of this legal category have been formed in scientific works today. The term "public safety" is widely used in various fields of scientific knowledge and in the practical activities of executive authorities, as well as law enforcement agencies. However, despite its widespread use, unfortunately, today there is no unified approach to the definition of "public safety". In this regard, it is appropriate to comprehensively analyze scientific literature and current legal documents to determine the meaning of the concept of "public safety".

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